

Measuring the circularity potential of an eco-friendly touristic facility in a Mediterranean island

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Abstract: Green Infrastructure, Nature-based Solutions (NbS) and biomimicry can be seen as sustainable solutions tackling the problem of reduced water availability and jeopardized water quality by enabling water reuse and recycling. However, the lack of a holistic methodological framework assessing water systems (combination of centralized, decentralized and NbS) is limiting their transferability and wider implementation. The current work aims at the development and application of a circular assessment methodology of such systems, taking into consideration metabolic profiles of water, and water-related energy and nutrients, environmental impacts, socio-economic values and products valorization pathways. Performance indicators that can be used as metrics of sustainability and circularity were derived. The methodology was applied in an eco-friendly touristic facility (Eco-lodge) in Tinos Island, Greece enabling the quantification of the proposed indicators with validated data, as well as assessment of the costs and benefits of the hybrid water system.

Keywords: Sustainability and Circularity Assessment; Nature-based Solutions; Water and Nutrients Reuse & Recycling;

Introduction: In the Mediterranean region, the rising domestic, industrial, and agricultural water demands superimpose on the uneven distribution of water supplies causing an increased water stress (Capone et al., 2012). Climate change is furthermore considered to exacerbate water scarcity (Roson and Damania, 2017). In order to protect and enhance nature and natural processes, as well as to promote a long-term sustainability, the European Commission has invested in GI and NbS as tools that simultaneously provide environmental, economic and social benefits (Faivre et al., 2017). These solutions further enable water and nutrients reuse and recycling, highlighting the link to the concept of circular economy (Voulvoulis, 2018). Efforts have been made to evaluate the performance of such solutions focusing on their costs and benefits by either proposing indicators that have not been applied in operational environment (Calliari et al., 2019), or by assessing one specific solution (Zolch et al., 2017). The focus of the current work is on the development and application (at operational environment) of a holistic methodology to assess the sustainable and circular performance of hybrid water systems (decentralised GI, NbS and biomimicry solutions coupled to a conventional water system).

Materials and Methods: The methodological framework was based on the concepts of Urban Water Metabolism and Material Flow Analysis, LCA, Harvest to Harvest Approach, and LCC and Cost-benefit Analysis.

Case Study: The developed methodology was applied in an eco-friendly touristic facility (Eco-lodge) in Tinos Island, Greece. In Tinos Eco-lodge drinking water supplied from the centralized network is used for potable uses only, whereas off-grid solutions are implemented to cover the domestic and agricultural water needs.

Results and Discussion: The coupling of the concepts mentioned in Materials and Methods section enabled the consideration of metabolic water, water-related energy and nutrients flows, environmental impacts, enhancement of ecosystem services, socio-economic values, and valorisation pathways. Circularity and sustainability indicators were derived from this assessment and they were successfully quantified with validated data of Tinos Eco-lodge. Figure 1 illustrates the water balances in Tinos Eco-lodge Water System.

Figure 1: Basic Water flows in Eco-lodge Water System

Conclusions: A holistic methodology assessing the sustainability and circular performance of hybrid water systems was developed in order to address water scarcity. Qualitative and quantitative performance indicators were derived and validated with real data. The methodology was applied in an eco-friendly touristic facility, where centralized and off-grid solutions are used, evaluating the sustainability and circular potential of the studied water system.

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